

Spectrophotometric Method for Determination of Palladium(II), Gold(III) and Ruthenium(III) with 8-Methoxy-2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde thiosemicarbazone

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There is an increasing interest in the spectrophotometric determination of palladium(II)¹, and gold(III)², ruthenium(III), rhodium(III) and palladium(II)³.

In the present work, 8-methoxy-2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (8-Meo-QAT) has been used for determination of Pd^{II}, Au^{III} and Ru^{III} in various metal mixtures.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of the reagent (8-Meo-QAT) in DMF-water (1 : 1) exhibit absorption maximum at 360 nm with molar extinction coefficient of $3.62 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at pH 4. The absorption of the metal complexes containing 1 ml of metal solution (1 mg ml^{-1}) and 1.6 ml of $3.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ reagent was recorded. The colour and absorption remained constant and stable for 24 h. The absorption maxima for the Pd^{II}, Ru^{III} and Au^{III} complexes are 435, 390, 390 nm at pH 4, 6 and 1 respectively.

The optimum amounts of the reagent solution ($3.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$) needed for Pd^{II}, Au^{III} and Ru^{III} are 1.4, 1.0 and 1.0 ml respectively. Beer's law is obeyed upto 4–5 ppm of Pd^{II}, 9–11 ppm of Au^{III} and 9–11 ppm of Ru^{III}. Sandell's sensitivity⁴ values are $0.1498 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ for Pd^{II}, $0.1578 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ for Au^{III} and $0.1192 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ for Ru^{III}. The metal : 8-Meo-QAT ratios of the complexes are 1 : 1 for Au^{III} and 1 : 2 for Pd^{II} and Ru^{III}.

The effect of diverse ions were studied. For determination of Pd^{II} (2 ppm), the tolerance limits (ppm) for different ions are as follows : Ni^{II} (215), Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} (200), Ba^{II} (160), Ru^{III} (7), Cr^{III} and Cu^{II} (50), Fe^{III} (10), Co^{II} (110), Hg^{II} and Au^{III} (2), Pb^{II} (130), Sn^{II} (25), Mo^{VI} (100), Cd^{II} (3), V^V (4), citrate (1400), EDTA (570), thiosulphate (110) and urea (1000), while tartarate does not interfere. For Au^{III} (2 ppm), the tolerance limits (ppm) are : Ni^{II}, Ru^{III} and Hg^{II} (2), Mn^{II} (250), Ba^{II} (50), Cr^{III} (40), Pb^{II} (25), Sn^{II} and Cu^{II} (20), Mo^{VI} (5), EDTA (250), urea (200), while Zn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Cd^{II}, V^V, citrate, tartarate and thiosulphate do not interfere. For Ru^{III} (2 ppm), the tolerance limits (ppm) are : Ni^{II} (2), Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} (250), Cr^{III} (2), Co^{II} (50), Hg^{II} (1), Sn^{II} (20), Mo^{VI} (50), Cu^{II} (10), EDTA (10), urea (600), while Ba^{II}, Ru^{III}, Fe^{III}, Au^{III}, Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, V^V, citrate, tartarate and thiosulphate do not interfere.

The applicability of the method was tested by satisfactory analysis of synthetic samples containing Pd. The proposed method is simple and rapid and it takes 10 min for Pd determination.

Experimental

Electronic spectra were recorded on an Elico CL-27 spectrophotometer and ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 783R spectrophotometer.

The reagent (8-Meo-2-chloro-QAT) was prepared by standard method⁵ by refluxing 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde and thiosemicarbazide in minimum amount of ethanol for 1 h, m.p. 187° (Found : C, 48.86; H, 3.72; N, 19.02%); ν_{max} 3420, 3320, 3160 (NH), 1620 (C=N), 1590–1595 (C=C), 1100 (C–O–C), 750 cm^{-1} (C–Cl).

The stock solutions (1 mg ml^{-1}) of Au^{III}, Pd^{II} and Ru^{III} were standardised. Buffer solution was prepared from 0.2 N acetic acid and 0.2 N sodium acetate.

An aliquot of solution the containing 5 ppm of Pd^{II}, Au^{III} or Ru^{III} was added to $3.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ reagent solution (1.6 ml) and buffer (1 ml) to adjust suitable pH. It was diluted to 10 ml with 20% DMF in water and the absorbance measured against the reagent blank.

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References

1. J. P. PEREZ TRUJILLO, Z. SOSA and J. J. ARIAS, *Polyhedron*, 1989, 8, 197; J. VOSTOVA and L. SOMMER, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1976, 41, 197; F. G. MONTELONGO, V. G. DIAZ and C. R. T. GONZALEZ, *Analysis*, 1981, 9, 353.
2. P. K. DAS and H. K. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1993, 70, 86.
3. A. CHOWDHURY, H. R. DAS and S. C. SHOME, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, 69, 796; B. K. PURI and M. GAUTAM, *Talanta*, 1978, 25, 484; A. BASEV, R. K. BANSAL, M. SATAKE and B. K. PURI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1983, 56, 3603.
4. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", 3rd. ed., Interscience, New York, 1959.
5. O. METH-COHN, B. ALARINE and B. TARNOWSKI, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1981, 1520.